

Supplement 1 – *In-silico* validation

Table 1 S1 *In-silico* validation of different primer pairs..... 1

Table 2-S2 mismatch analysis of alleles published in Monecke et al. (2012) 2

Table 1 S1 *In-silico* validation of different primer pairs

Pair	Sequence (5'-3') of Primer (F & R)		Length	GC	Tm	No. of nucleotide for*			Amplicon size	No. of mismatching nucleotides		No. of sequences**	Target gene
No.			(bp)	(%)	(°C)	HP	SC 3'	SC	(bp)	<i>mecA</i>	<i>mecA1</i>	with 100% similarity	
1	F	AAAAGATAAATCTTGGGGTG	20	35	52,3	5	-	-	525	0	0	> 500	Universal (1)
	R	CCTTGTTTCAT[Y]TTGAGTTC	20	35-40	52,3-54,3	-	-	-		0	0	> 500	
2	F	AAAATCGATGGTAAAGGTTGGC	22	41	58,4	-	-	-	533	0	3	> 500	<i>mecA</i> (1, 2)
	R	AGTTCTGCAGTACCGGATTTGC	22	50	62,1	-	-	9		0	4	> 500	
3	F	GAAATGACTGAACGTCCGATA	21	43	57,5	-	-	-	711	0	5	> 500	<i>mecA</i> This study
	R	ATAGCCATCTTCATGTTGGAGC	22	45	60,1	-	-	-		0	7	> 500	
4	F	TGGCTATCGTGTCACAATCG	20	50	58,4	0	0	7	310	0	5	> 500	<i>mecA</i> (3, 4) ^c
	R	CTGGAAC TTGTTGAGCAGAG	20	50	58,4	0	0	0		0	5	> 500	
5	F	TCACCAGGTTCAAC[Y]CAAAA	20	40-45	54,3-56,4	-	-	7	356	0	1	> 500	<i>mecA</i> (5)
	R	CCTGAATC[W]GCTAATAATATTTTC	23	30	55,5	-	-	9		0	2	> 500	
6	F	GTAGAAATGACTGAACGTCCGATAA	25	40	62,5	-	-	-	310	0	5	> 500	<i>mecA</i> (6-9)
	R	CCAATTCCACATTGTTTCGGTCTAA	25	40	62,5	4	-	-		0	5	> 500	
7	F	GGGATCATAGCGTCATTATTC	21	43	57,5	-	-	-	527	0	5	> 500	<i>mecA</i> (10)
	R	AACGATTGTGACACGATAGCC	21	48	59,5	-	-	6		0	4	> 500	
8	F	TGCTATCCACCTCAAACAGG	21	52	62,1	-	-	-	286	0	4	> 500	<i>mecA</i> (11)
	R	AACGTTGTAACCAACCCAAGA	21	48	59,5	-	-	-		0	2	> 500	
9	F	TCCAGATTACAACCTCACCAGG	22	45	60,1	-	-	-	162	0	3	> 500	<i>mecA</i> (12)
	R	CCACTTCATATCTTGTAACG	20	40	54,3	-	-	-		0	2	> 500	

10	F	GGCAATATTACCGCACCTCA	20	50	58,4	-	-	-	214	1	6	260 (95% similarity)	<i>mecA</i>	(13)
	R	GTCTGCCACTTTCTCCTTGT	20	50	58,4	-	-	-		1	6	4		
11	F	TGAGGTGCGTTAATATTGC	19	42	53	-	-	-	169	0	5	> 500	<i>mecA</i>	(14)
	R	GCAAACCTTAATTGGCAAATC	20	35	52,3	-	-	7		0	3	> 500		
	Pr-1	CTATTAACCTGATGGTATGCAACAAGTCG	28	39	65,6	-	-	-		0	4	> 500		
	Pr-2	CCAGTACAGATCCTTTCAATCTATAGCG	28	43	67,2	4	-	7		0	6	^b		
12	F	AAAATCGATGGTAAAGGTTGG	21	38	55,4	0	0	0	532	0	3	> 500	<i>mecA</i>	(15, 16)
	R	AGTTCTGCAGTACCGGATTTG	21	48	59,5	0	0	9		0	4	> 500		
13	F	CAGACCGCCCTATTAAGATT	20	45	56,4	-	-	-	466	7	0	44	<i>mecA1</i>	This study
	R	TGAACAGTCTTGAGAGGGACG	21	52	61,2	-	-	-		6	0	60		
14	F	ATTAATCATCGCCATCGTGA	20	40	54,3	-	-	-	663	10	0	29	<i>mecA1</i>	(1)
	R	TTTGTATCTTGATTCATATTTTGAACA	27	22	57,6	-	-	8		8	3	39		
15	F	AAAATCGATGGTAAAGGTTGGC	22	41	58,4	-	-	-	533	0	3		<i>mecA1</i> ^a	(17)
	R	AGTTCTGCAGTACCGGATTTGC	22	50	62,1	-	-	9		0	4			

a) probably incorrect designation, this primer pair binds *mecA* not *mecA1* (see Frey et al., 2013 (1), primer pair no. 3)

b) the position of this sequence is not within amplicons

c) Primer sequence contains a typo in the publication (4) - the original sequence is from Galdiero et al., 2003 (3)

Please note that use of primers by others is only cursorily reported and by no means complete

Table 2-S2 mismatch analysis of alleles published in Monecke et al., 2012 (14)

Designation	Allele no.	GenBank entries ^b	Species	Number of mismatches								comments (Sievers et al.)			
				Primer 1 (1)		Primer 2 (1)		Primer 3 This study		Primer 4 (3)			Primer 5 (1)		Primer 6 This study
				universal- <i>mecA</i>		<i>mecA</i>		<i>mecA</i>		<i>mecA1</i>		<i>mecA1</i>			
				F	R	F	R	F	R	F	R	F	R		
<i>mecA_AB037671</i>	1	AB037671.1 , AEEK01000041.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	9
<i>mecA_AB221119</i>	2	AB221119.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6
<i>mecA_AB546266</i>	3	AB546266.1	<i>S. fleurettii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	7	7	6
<i>mecA_AM048805</i>	8	AM048804.2 , AM048805.2	<i>S. capitis</i> , <i>S. kloosii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	7	7	6

<i>mecA_FN433596</i>	19	FN433596.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6	
<i>mecA_GU235983</i>	22	GU235983.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6	
<i>mecA_GU370073</i>	24	AB033763.2, AB047089.2, AB096217.1, AB221120.1, AB221123.1, AB236888.1, AB245471.1, AB266532.1, AB266533.1, AB353724.1, AB373032.1, AB425824.1, ACSN01000041.1, ACYP01000048.1, ACZQ01000131.1, AF411935.3, AM048802.2, AM048803.2, AM904731.1, AY271717.1, CP000046.1, DQ106887.1, GU370073.1 , LCL_10002.1, Y13096.1	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>S. cohnii</i> , <i>S. kloosii</i> , <i>S. pseudintermedius</i> , <i>S. saprophyticus</i> , <i>S. sciuri</i> , <i>S. vitulinus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6	
<i>mecA_YI3095</i>	31	YI3095.1	<i>S. sciuri</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6	
<i>mecA_AB546267</i>	4	AB546267.1	<i>S. fleurettii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6	
<i>mecA_AB546780^a</i>	5	AB546780.1	<i>S. vitulinus</i>	0	0	4	2	2	1	2	1	13	8	4	5	
<i>mecA_AB547235^a</i>	6	AB547235.1	<i>S. sciuri</i>	0	0	5	4	4	6	4	5	0	0	1	1 = <i>mecA1</i>	
<i>mecA_AB547236^a</i>	7	AB547236.1	<i>S. sciuri</i>	0	0	3	4	5	7	5	5	0	3	0	0 = <i>mecA1</i>	
<i>mecA_YI3094^a</i>	30	YI3094.1	<i>S. sciuri</i>	0	0	3	4	5	7	5	5	0	3	0	0 = <i>mecA1</i>	
<i>mecA_AM048807</i>	9	AM048806.2 , AM048807.2	<i>S. capitis</i> , <i>S. kloosii</i>	0	0	4	2	2	1	2	1	13	8	4	5	
<i>mecA_AM048808</i>	10	AM048808.2 , AM048809.2, AM048810.2, AM048811.2	<i>S. capitis</i> , <i>S. kloosii</i> , <i>S. vitulinus</i>	0	0	4	2	2	1	2	1	13	8	4	5	
<i>mecA_AY786579</i>	11	AY786579.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6	
<i>mecA_ABSA01000066</i>	13	AB063172.2, AB063173.1, AB221121.1, AB221122.1, AB221124.1, AB245470.1, AB266531.1, AB425823.1, AB539727.1, ABSA01000066.1, ACHE01000063.1, ACHH02000005.1, ACJC01000132.1, ACKC01000025.1, ACKD01000060.1, ACKE01000035.1, ACKF01000035.1, ACKJ01000051.1, ACKK01000007.1,	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i> , <i>S. pseudintermedius</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6

		ACKL01000046.1, ACOT01000006.1, ACSO01000033.1, ADAT01000064.1, ADJI01000031.1, ADJJ01000027.1, ADJK01000025.1, ADMU01000036.1, AJ810120.1, AJ810121.1 , AM904732.1, AM943017.1, AP009324.1, BA000033.2, BABM01000001.1, BX571856.1, CABA01000047.1, CP000029.1, CP000255.1, CP000703.1, CP000730.1, CP000736.1, CP001844.2, CP002110.1, CP002114.2, CP002120.1, EF596937.1, EU437549.2, EU437550.1, FJ390057.1, FJ670542.1, GQ918137.1, GU122149.1, GU451305.1, GU451306.1, GU451307.1, HM030720.1, HM030721.1, X52592.1													
<i>mecA_BA000018</i>	14	BA000017.4 , BA000018.3, D86934.2, EU333401.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6
<i>mecA_EU929081</i>	15	EU929081.1	<i>S. pseudintermedius</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6
<i>mecA_EU929082</i>	16	EU929082.1	<i>S. pseudintermedius</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6
<i>mecA_GU235984</i>	23	GU235984.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6
<i>mecA_AY820253</i>^a	12	AY820253.1	<i>S. sciuri</i>	0	0	5	5	5	6	5	5	2	1	0	0 = <i>mecA1</i>
<i>mecA_EU929079</i>	17	EU929079.1	<i>S.pseudintermedius</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6
<i>mecA_EU929080</i>	18	EU929080.1	<i>S.pseudintermedius</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	9
<i>mecA_Y00688</i>	27	Y00688.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	9
<i>mecA_GQ902038</i>	20	AB121219.1, AB353125.1, AB437289.1, AB437290.1, AB462393.1, AB478780.1, AM292304.1, AM990992.1, AP006716.1, AY894415.1, FJ544922.1, GQ902038.1	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>S. haemolyticus</i> , <i>S. pseudintermedius</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	6
<i>mecA_GU227428</i>	21	GU227428.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	9

<i>mecA_Y14051</i>	32	X52593.1, Y14051.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	8	7	9	
<i>mecA_LGA251</i>	25	FR821779.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	5	3	5	5	9	10	9	4	10	12	9	10	will not be amplified by any
<i>mecA_FR823292</i>	26	FR823292.1	<i>S. aureus</i>	5	3	5	5	9	10	9	4	10	12	9	10	will not be amplified by any
<i>mecA_Y09223</i>	28	AB547234.1, Y09223.1	<i>S. sciuri</i>	0	0	3	4	5	6	5	5	0	3	0	0	= <i>mecA1</i>
<i>mecA_Y13052^a</i>	29	Y13052.1	<i>S. sciuri</i>	1	0	5	4	4	6	4	5	1	0	1	1	= <i>mecA1</i>

a) bold: those sequences that had mismatches in the intended primer-binding region

b) marked in red: those sequences that had been used for alignment

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